

The 5n-vector ensemble method

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Abstract

We present a multiple test for the targeted search of continuous gravitational waves from an ensemble of known pulsars in LIGO-Virgo data, combining multidetector single pulsar statistics defined through the 5n-vector method. In order to maximize the detection probability, we describe a rank truncation method to select the most promising sources within the ensemble, based on the p-values computed from single pulsar analysis. We also present two different sensitivity tests, using hardware and software injections, to show the improvement in the detection probability.

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Introduction

Isolated spinning neutron stars, sometimes observed as pulsars, are possible emitters of gravitational waves if not symmetric with respect to the rotation axis. The emitted continuous gravitational wave (CW) signals, are persistent and quasi-monochromatic over long time-scales and could be detected by terrestrial interferometric detectors.

In the CW targeted search, the source parameters (sky position, frequency and frequency derivatives) are assumed to be known with high accuracy; this is for instance the case of known pulsars, where the source parameters are measured from the emitted electromagnetic radiation. In the single harmonic emission scenario, the gravitational wave frequency is expected to be exactly twice the rotation frequency of the star.

In [1], the LIGO-Virgo Collaboration presented the latest results for the targeted search of CWs from 236 pulsars with rotation frequencies above 10 Hz, using LIGO and Virgo data from the second and the third observing runs, showing no evidence for gravitational-wave emission from any pulsar at either frequency. For only 23 pulsars the obtained results entail upper limit on the gravitational wave amplitude that are lower than the theoretical pulsars’ spin-down limit.

In this context, this work tries to improve the detection efficiency for the targeted search of continuous gravitational waves considering an ensemble - i.e. a set - of weak sources that are individually undetectable. The improvement in the detection probability refers to the combined signal from the ensemble and not to the single signal detection capability.

Methods to detect gravitational waves from an ensemble of known pulsars have already been presented in [2] combining F-statistic, in [3, 4] combining 5-vector statistics from individual pulsar, and in [5]

using a Hierarchical Bayesian procedure.

In this work, we describe and test the rank truncation method proposed in [4] to optimize the detection probability combining multi-detector single pulsar statistics, defined through the 5n-vector method [6, 7].

The ensemble procedure

Let us consider an ensemble of N pulsars and indicate with \bar{S}_i the measured value of the detection statistic S_i for the i -th pulsar (with $i = 1, \dots, N$). In this work, we will consider the normalized definition (see [4]) of the statistics S_i defined by the 5n-vector method. In the case of Gaussian noise, the normalized S_i distribution does not depend on pulsar or detectors parameters and it is a Gamma distribution with integer shape and scale parameters: $\Gamma(x; 2, 1)$. Let us indicate with P_i the p-value inferred from the single pulsar analysis $P_i = P(S_i \geq \bar{S}_i | noise)$.

The proposed rank truncation method ranks the pulsars in the ensemble according to the p-values P_i , since smaller p-values correspond to higher probability for a signal. Ranking pulsars for increasing p-values is equal to rank pulsars for decreasing values of the single pulsar statistic (since the noise distributions are the same):

$$\bar{S}_{(1)} < \bar{S}_{(2)} < \dots < \bar{S}_{(N)} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{S}_{(j)}$ indicates the j -th smallest measured value for the detection statistic for a certain pulsar in the ensemble. For an ensemble of N pulsars with $(P_j \leq P_i \forall i)$ and $(P_k \geq P_i \forall i)$, the smallest and the largest order statistics are $\bar{S}_{(1)} \equiv \bar{S}_k$ and $\bar{S}_{(N)} \equiv \bar{S}_j$, respectively.

By considering $\bar{S}_{(i)}$ as a single realization of the order statistic $S_{(i)}$, we can control the look-elsewhere effect [8] since the $S_{(i)}$ distribution depends on N , the number of measured statistics (i.e the number of analyzed pulsars).

In [4], we proposed the partial sum $T(k)$ of the order statistics $S_{(i)}$,

$$T(k) = \sum_{i=N-k+1}^N S_{(i)} \quad (2)$$

as the ensemble detection statistic for the rank truncation method. Indeed, the $T(k)$ distributions depend on N for each k ; in this way, we can combine pulsars with the smallest p-values that are assumed near the detection threshold.

Even in the simple case of Gaussian noise (that means $S_i \sim \Gamma(x; 2, 1)$) the convolution of Gamma order statistics has no simple expression. For $k = N$, $T(N)$ is the simple sum of the N Gamma random variables since the order is no more important. It follows that: $T(N) \sim \Gamma(x; 2N, 1)$. To infer the $T(k)$ noise distributions for each k , we used a Monte Carlo procedure starting from the noise distribution of S_i [4]. In the case of real data, we consider the S_i experimental noise distribution inferred from a set of off-source frequencies in a small frequency band (≈ 0.2 Hz) around the expected on-source frequencies.

Reconstructing the $T(k)$ noise distributions for each k , we can compute the p-value of ensemble $P(k)$ as a function of k :

$$P(k) = P(T(k) \geq \bar{T}(k) | noise) \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{T}(k) = \sum_{i=N-k+1}^N \bar{S}_{(i)} \quad (3)$$

Fixing a set of N sources, we can compute the N p-values from the single pulsar analysis and define the $T(k)$ statistic, a p-value of ensemble as a function of k . It is important to stress that k is the number of order statistics with the k smallest p-values, rather than the number of pulsars. In the next Sections, we will describe two different tests of the proposed procedure using hardware/software injections and the O3 dataset for the LIGO Livingston Observatory (LLO).

Test with hardware injections

To test the ensemble procedure, we use hardware injections and the O3 LLO dataset. Hardware injections are simulated gravitational-wave signals added to the detector by physically displacing the detectors test masses in order to simulate the effects of a CW signal. Considering the entire O3 dataset, the hardware injections can be easily detected due to their very high signal to noise ratio. Using the Band Sample Data framework [9], we can fix the smallest datasets (1 day long) to have hardware injections that can not be detected with high significance. Then, we can consider an ensemble of different days and perform, for each day, a targeted search for a fixed hardware injection. Using the obtained results, we construct the statistics $T(k)$ and compute the ensemble p-value as a function of k . In this test, we fix the hardware injection (Pulsar3 in [10]) and consider an ensemble with $N = 20$ of consecutive 1-day long datasets starting from 15/08/2019.

Figure 1: *Top-left plot* Fitted shape (red triangle) and scale parameters (blue square) using a Gamma distribution to the experimental S_i noise distribution for the i -th pulsar, inferred using a range of off-source frequencies. *Top-right plots* Fitted shape and scale parameters (dashed lines) with 95% confidence level (coloured area) for the $T(k)$ noise distributions for each k inferred from the Monte Carlo procedure. *Bottom plot* P-value of ensemble (blue line) $P(k)$ defined in (3) compared with the single pulsar p-value, ranked for increasing values.

Figure 1 shows a summary plot for the analysis of ensemble; the top-left plot shows the scale and

shape parameters of the Gamma distribution fitted to the experimental S_i noise distributions (where i is the index of the day), the top-right plots show the results of the fits using a Gamma distribution for the $T(k)$ noise distributions for each k while the bottom plot compare the ordered P_i (red dots) with the p-value of ensemble $P(k)$ (blue line).

As shown in Figure 1, the p-values for each day are consistent with the noise hypothesis while the p-value of ensemble is well below the 1% threshold showing clear evidence for a signal from the ensemble.

Tests with software injections

In this Section, we describe two tests using software injections. We consider a set of $N = 100$ fake pulsars with random parameters, expected gravitational wave frequency f_{gw} in the range [100,110] Hz and injected amplitude H defined as a fraction α of the minimum detectable amplitude for the targeted search h_{min} (see [11])

$$H = \alpha \cdot h_{min} \approx \alpha \cdot 10.4 \sqrt{\frac{S(f_{gw})}{T_{obs}}} \quad (4)$$

where $S(f_{gw})$ is the one-sided power spectral density at the expected gravitational wave frequency and T_{obs} is the detector observation time.

Figure 2: Ensemble of 100 simulated pulsars with no signal. *Top-left plot* Fitted shape (red triangle) and scale parameters (blue square) using a Gamma distribution to the experimental S_i noise distribution for the i -th pulsar, inferred using a range of off-source frequencies. *Top-right plots* Fitted shape and scale parameters (dashed lines) with 95% confidence level (coloured area) for the $T(k)$ noise distributions for each k inferred from the Monte Carlo procedure. *Bottom plot* P-value of ensemble (blue line) $P(k)$ defined in (3) compared with the single pulsar p-value, ranked for increasing values.

In Figure 2, we do not inject any signals to check the performance of the procedure in case of only noise. The fitted shape and scale parameters are almost 2 and 1 respectively (top-left plot) since the pulsars' f_{gw} are in a frequency band where the O3 data are almost stationary and Gaussian. This is shown also in the top-right plots since for $k = N$, $T(N)$ is the simple sum of N Gamma random variables and $T(N) \sim \Gamma(x; 2N, 1)$.

The ensemble p-value $P(k)$ are full consistent with noise as expected. The single pulsar p-values P_i are also consistent with noise with 1 pulsar with a p-value below the 1%, as expected for an ensemble of $N = 100$ pulsars.

Figure 3: Ensemble of 100 simulated pulsars with only 10 signals, each with single test detection probability of $\sim 25\%$. *Top-left plot* Fitted shape (red triangle) and scale parameters (blue square) using a Gamma distribution to the experimental S_i noise distribution for the i -th pulsar, inferred using a range of off-source frequencies. *Top-right plots* Fitted shape and scale parameters (dashed lines) with 95% confidence level (coloured area) for the $T(k)$ noise distributions for each k inferred from the Monte Carlo procedure. *Bottom plot* P-value of ensemble (blue line) $P(k)$ defined in (3) compared with the single pulsar p-value, ranked for increasing values.

In Figure 3, we consider only 10 pulsars, out of 100, with an associated signal. The α value for each signal is 0.5, that corresponds to a detection probability for the single pulsar analysis of almost 25%.

The single pulsar p-values show no clear evidence of a signal, with the exception of five pulsars with P_i between 0.3% and 1%. The ensemble p-value has a minimum at $k \approx 10$ with $P(10) \approx 0.2\%$ with the expected shape as shown in [4] for simulated data (see Figure 5).

The ensemble p-value shows no strong evidence of a signal from the considered ensemble but it returns some hints and strong motivation for a follow-up at least for the pulsars with the smallest p-values. The V-shape for $P(k)$ in Figure 3 justifies the proposed rank truncation method to optimize the detection probability if few signals are present into the analyzed ensemble.

Conclusion

In [4], we have proposed a rank truncation method for the targeted search of CW signal from an ensemble of pulsars. Since we expect few signals near the detection threshold, we rank pulsars according to the single pulsar p-values and construct a detection statistic as the partial sum of the ordered values of the single pulsar statistics. These are defined by the 5n-vector method but the procedure can be easily generalized to different pipelines.

Considering real data using the BSD framework and the O3 dataset for LLO, we test the proposed method using hardware and software injections considering three different cases. In Figure 1, we consider hardware injections in small datasets that can be detected only using an ensemble procedure. In Figure 2, we test the noise case with no injected signals while in Figure 3, we consider only 10 signals in the ensemble of 100 fake pulsars. The results show an improvement in the detection probability also in the case of real data confirming the theoretical results obtained in [4].

In the future, we plan to test how the detection probability of the statistics $T(k)$ depends on the number of analyzed pulsars N for a fixed number of signals in the ensemble.

We plan to apply the ensemble procedure to the O3 dataset for the LIGO-Virgo detectors and to the set of known pulsars analyzed in [1].

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